

COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL ABILITIES IN STUDENTS OF CHILDREN'S MUSIC SCHOOLS IN PIANO LESSONS

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Annotation: The article examines the problem of comprehensive development of musical abilities of students in children's music schools during piano lessons.

Key words: ear for music, intellectual activity, sense of rhythm, shades.

Comprehensive promotion of intellectual and auditory concepts of a student of a children's music school should be carried out from the first lessons. It should begin with the formation of a musical worldview, which subsequently determines success in performance. Musical ear, which contains several components, is of great importance in the formation of a future pianist. Let us separately highlight the importance of inner ear, which involves understanding music without performing it on a musical instrument. We consider the formation of the skill of controlling one's own voice and ear to be an important stage in the process of developing relative and absolute ear. The skill of transposition, which eventually acquires a purely technical skill, is based on auditory activity.

Intellectual activity in analyzing a musical work ensures the achievement of high quality performance. It involves not only understanding the musical text at the piano, but also knowledge of the text without the piano, for example, performance on a table, when not only the motor-motor system is involved, but also the brain, which is able to control the content of the text.

Auditory development, as an important factor in the formation of a musician, has become one of the main areas of music pedagogy and performance in recent times. It is the auditory skills that allow the future pianist to navigate the world musical culture, rich in its national schools and styles. The image that the pianist hears motivates the performance in the process of creating an impeccable image of the performed work.

The next, important stage in the formation of complex musical abilities is the work on the formation of a sense of rhythm. This is very painstaking work and presupposes a certain methodological basis that has developed in music pedagogy. In piano lessons, we use numerous templates of rhythmic tasks that combine such components as movement to music with singing the text. Rhythmic abilities are actively promoted with the involvement of game components that are aimed not only at developing fine motor skills, but also the entire body of the beginning pianist.

Separately, it is necessary to dwell on ensemble play, which is of great importance in the complex development of the musical abilities of a beginning pianist. This type of creativity contains enormous potential in the appearance of an emotional component in the performance of a musical work. Noise orchestras with the division of performers into personal rhythmic formulas are very popular. The creation of a highly artistic musical image on the piano is possible with the use of dynamic shades, pedal, and certain sound extraction

methods. Knowledge of such signs as forte, piano, crescendo, diminuendo, marcato, recorded in musical texts, significantly influences the process of forming the intellectual, auditory, and performing skills of students.

A concert performance of the program at the end of the school year has a great influence on the development of the individual qualities of the performer, when the beginning pianists get acquainted with each other's creative achievements, learn new pieces from classical music, and are inspired by each other's results. All this significantly enriches the educational process and creates new horizons for creativity.

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